

Constructing Brand Personality from the TripAdvisor Online Reviews

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Abstract: The research focuses on utilizing the unstructured dataset and the exploratory factor analysis to construct the brand personality of a sample hotel in Bali. Online reviews delivered by the consumers in TripAdvisor were collected within the 2019 - 2021 period of observation, further data cleaning was conducted. The results show that there are four dimensions, and there are missing competence dimensions within the dataset. This is a unique finding because the five dimensions usually exist in the hotel dataset in some other studies using the same method. There are five dimensions of brand personality, namely sincerity, sophistication, excitement, ruggedness, competence. Moreover, sincerity dominates within the dataset.

Keywords: Brand Personality, Online Reviews, Content Analysis, Big Data, Bali

I. INTRODUCTION

Today the consumers are engaging with social media; they are posting their experience on consuming the product and services, furthermore these online reviews also will influence others that are reading and looking for information into the product and services. All of this information whether it text, photos, videos, audios are calls the user generated content. Since it is a content from the consumers, therefore brand and company should pay attention on the user generated content[1].

Technology accelerating improvement breed a huge amount of information related to the user generated content. One of the website or application that become the bank or the place for the online reviews on hospitality, travel and tourism is the TripAdvisor. The TripAdvisor is the source of information that observe in this research. The information in the TripAdvisor is an unstructured data set that different compare with the structure dataset [2][3, 4].

Unstructured data set is understood as the information that needn't have a predefined redefined manner [5]. The online reviews in the TripAdvisor are not an organized information. But it is the information based on the consumer willingness to write, related to his or her preference on reviewing the attributes that are interesting for the consumer[6].

Therefore, it is a new kind of data set compare with the survey, which have a defined question deliver to the respondent. And the respondent shall only answer based on those questions within the questionnaire. Since this is a different kind of dataset, but the rich and the vanity information is so enormous therefore this is a new opportunity for either marketing and also the company manager to utilize the data for the benefit of the company [7].

The user generated content is developing the brand perceived by the consumers. Furthermore, in this digital age, consumer will look forward in their social media for the benefits and also engage with the brand personality that relate with the consumer. This kind of brand personality is merely important to distinguish between one product compare with the other product.

Therefore, the company and also the marketing scientist should consider the online reviews in the TripAdvisor platform as a range of information that should be utilized for further evaluation and also probably related to the brand of the hotel or the destination [8-10].

II. REVIEW LITERATURE

The research focus on the utilization of the unstructured dataset and the exploratory factor analysis of the brand personality.

2.1 Unstructured Textual data

Online reviews delivered by the consumers in the TripAdvisor is an unstructured data. It means that within a sentence, there are some multiple data points that comes from one activity which is the experience delivered by the consumer [5][11-13]. Therefore, from this data unit, we should make a categorization. Each information should be separated, tabulated and then prepared for the quantitative analysis [14].

2.2 Brand Personality

Every product and services have a brand personality. Personality that are constructing the product and services by acting as an individual or a human that living and engage with the consumers. Therefore, there are personalities such as Sincerity, Sophistication, Excitement, Competence, and Ruggedness as the dimension of the personality that consist of many words that categorize in the dimension [15][16][17][18]. Sincerity is the dimension that shows the performance of the services to the consumer. Excitement is the dimension relate to the newness of the experience. The sophistication dimension relates to the outstanding experience of the resort. The competence dimension relates to the performance of the services. The ruggedness is the dimension that relates to the natural experience[16].

This is how the construction of a brand based on what the consumersaid to the platform TripAdvisor, moreover the research could also consider the brand personality based on the consumer perception that are in the TripAdvisor. Since there are many things and words delivered by the consumer, therefore all of those varieties of text shouldcategorizeinto dimension that construct the personality of the services are product.

III. RESEARCH METHOD

The process started with data collection, which is extracting the data from the TripAdvisor based on the period of the observation. This research focus on the 2019 until 2021. Since this is a qualitative research, using a textual online review, therefore after the data is collected, further process of cleaning the data is conducted. After the process of the data collection and also the data cleansing conducted, further categorization based on the SSERC personality dimension conducted[15][16][17]. And finally the frequency related to the brand personality of the object observed with a utilization of Provalis [17].

Table 1. Research Method

Research Methodology	Exploratory study
Type of sampling	Nonstatistical sampling
Sample	2019 - 2021 dataset
Data collection methods	Extraction from user-generated content
Information sources	TripAdvisor online platform
Key contributors	Sample online reviews
Data analysis methods	Brand Personality exploratory factor analysis with Brand Personality Dictionary [18]
Study period	2019 - 2021
Source	Based on [18, 19]

IV. RESULTS

4.1. Brand Personality exploratory factor analysis

The summary show that there were five dimensions of brand personality in this analysis case, namely sincerity, sophistication, excitement, ruggedness, competence. Sincerity dominates the majority dimensionin the 2019 - 2021dataset (Table 4).

Table 4. Brand Personality Dimension Frequency

No	Dimension	Dimension Frequency
1	SINCERITY	489
2	SOPHISTICATION	234
3	EXCITEMENT	113
4	RUGGEDNESS	53
5	COMPETENCE	44

Sincerity

An example of this dimension is the case of (2) (TripAdvisor Feb 2021), who conveyed that the staff is very friendly with the keyword "friendly". Furthermore, the case of (6) (TripAdvisor Jan 2021) conveys that the room is good with the keyword "good" (Table 5).

Another example of a case is (12) (TripAdvisor Jan 2021), which says that the staff is good with the keyword "kind". Three of the above cases are reviews that have Positive sentiments. This dimension keyword is very closely related to the adjectives of the hotel staff obtained from the experience of the hotel visitors when interacting with their staff.

Another example is the case of (14) (TripAdvisor Jan 2021), who said that the hotel staff were accommodating, with the keyword "helpful". In addition, there is also a case example (22) (TripAdvisor Jan 2021) that the experience of staying at the hotel is pleasant, with the keyword "pleasant".

The case (32) (TripAdvisor Jan 2021) conveyed that he only stayed a few days at the hotel and had a great experience from the friendly staff as well as polite "polite". Therefore, he said he would return to the hotel. The keyword used is polite, which means that this review reveals the behavior or treatment of the staff he gained from his stay at the hotel, so without a doubt, he recommends others to stay here.

In addition, there is also a case of (182) (TripAdvisor Sep 2020) that all the staff are amiable and welcome their "welcoming" when they arrive at the hotel. In this category, many reviews feature Performance from staff appreciated by visitors to the hotel.

Another review was submitted by the case of (520) (TripAdvisor Nov 2019), who said that the hotel has accommodating staff and always smiles "smiling". In the context of the review conveyed, this keyword has a positive sentiment because smiling is a keyword that displays the performance of the staff appreciated by hotel visitors.

Table 5. Sincerity Dimension Keyword in Context

Case number	Pre-Keyword Context	Keyword	Post-Keyword Context
2	Very recommended...great view..great food..very great stay. Chicken pasta so delicious. This is the second time we stay here and so amazing. Kiusa, Desa very amazing ..	friendly	staff and great hospitality Will be back soon. Thank u [REDACTED]!!!!??

Sophistication

An example of this dimension can be seen from the case review (10) (TripAdvisor Jan 2021), which conveys the room at the hotel as very Beautiful with the keyword "beautiful". Furthermore, the case of (20) (TripAdvisor Jan 2021) conveys that the yoga class trainer at the hotel is a good teacher with the keyword "excellent". Thus, both reviews have a positive sentiment, which shows the hotel above-average service position and facility position.

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Another review was submitted by the case of (30) (TripAdvisor Jan 2021), who wanted to state this place is exclusive for those who are looking for tranquility with the keyword "exclusive". Exclusively, it places the hotel above average as a hotel with an advantage over other hotels.

In addition, the case of (60) (TripAdvisor Nov 2020) conveys that the rooms at the hotel are luxurious and spotless. Infinite pool facilities are also equipped with a floating pillow.

Another example is the case of (74) (TripAdvisor Nov 2020), who had such a wonderful "gorgeous" experience that he was satisfied with the experience of staying at the hotel and recommending the hotel to other visitors.

Excitement

An example of this dimension can be interpreted from the case (1) (TripAdvisor Mar 2021), which conveys if you want a quiet place and also fresh air "fresh" then this place is worth visiting. The fresh keyword is a word that has a positive sentiment and makes the spirit, novelty, freshness of the hotel.

An example of the case (22) (TripAdvisor Jan 2021) conveys that the structure and food are amazingly "crazy". However, this expression of the word crazy has a positive sentiment and means there is something extraordinary, excitement gained from the food provided by the hotel.

Case (48) (TripAdvisor Nov 2020) said that he only stayed one night and had an amazing "awesome" experience. The keyword use is incredible, which means this review expresses the spirit he gained from the experience of staying at the hotel.

In addition, there is also a case (100) (TripAdvisor Nov 2020) that the furniture and design in the hotel modern "modern" with traditional touches that make the hotel very beautiful. Therefore, he will also come back to this place because visitors have a pleasant experience while here.

Ruggedness

An example of this dimension can be interpreted from the case statement (76) (TripAdvisor Nov 2020), which conveys the beautiful wilderness landscape. The keyword is "jungle". In the dimension of brand personality by Aaker (1997), this jungle keyword reveals a personality that wants to blend with nature. This keyword is also positively defined by reviews on TripAdvisor.

Another example is presented by the case of (156) (TripAdvisor Sep 2020), who enjoyed the east-facing room so that it could enjoy the sunrise. Although the keyword used here is sunrise, it is also a keyword related to nature, so it goes into this dimension. These keywords, in the context of the reviews submitted, have a positive sentiment.

The case of (379) (TripAdvisor Dec 2019) is an example of a case with negative sentiment. The reviews convey that the hotel has excellent potential, but this review conveys that communication with the staff of the hotel is challenging, because the staff work slowly. The keyword used is "difficult" with negative sentiment. So, this review conveys at the end that the hotel can get five stars because of the excellent location and facilities, but the staff must develop the service even better.

Another example is the case of (506) (TripAdvisor Nov 2019) that the hotel is nestled among beautiful nature with bedrooms, bathrooms, and areas outside the "outdoor" villa perfect for relaxing.

V. CONCLUSION

In the case study, TripAdvisor review analysis for the hotels from 2019 to 2021 shows that this hotel does not have competence dimensions. Even though there are 44 units of words categorized incompetence, nevertheless these words are meaningless in competence dimension construction. It is an exciting finding because in some other studies using the same method, usually the five dimensions is existing. Competence itself is related to the ability of the brand to meet the needs of consumer services.

Nevertheless, the results of this Provalis software do not reveal any review competence. Whereas if we look at the reviews, there are keywords indicators of the dimension of competence that is helpful. Therefore, it is necessary to

develop better than the five-dimensional categorization process of Aaker using unstructured data created by Provalis software.

In addition, the results of this study show that the hotel is indeed vital in two personalities Sincerity and Sophistication. In the data of the hotel 2019 – 2021, the majority is dominated by Sincerity which means that the brand is seen as a humble, honest, trustworthy, and cheerful personality. Brands that provide sincere service commit to consumers or attention to consumer needs.

Category reviews with the second majority are Sophistication which means consumers perceive the brand as a person who has a class, high position, or glamour. This luxury is emitted from the personality of the brand with sophistication dimensions. This status is radiated to consumers. It becomes essential in the hotel context because it is associated with a house/ villa and a luxurious, classy, glittering place.

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